

A Systematic Review on the Detrimental Impact of Online Gaming on Physical and Psychological Well-being: Minacious than Drugs

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Online gaming has advanced into a prevalent digital phenomenon, offering entertainment and social connection but also upsurge in psychological and physical health concerns. This systematic review synthesizes empirical findings from 2009 to 2025 to evaluate the detrimental effects of online gaming addiction on mental well-being, academic performance, social connectedness, and physical health. The review highlights that excessive gaming links strongly with loneliness, depression, anxiety, irritability, poor sleep quality, and diminished empathy. Moreover, the growing prevalence of Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD), recognized by the WHO and ICD-11, underscores its clinical significance. Evidence suggests that prolonged gaming disrupts interpersonal relationships, reduces academic motivation, and contributes to maladaptive coping strategies among adolescents and young adults. Despite a minority of studies acknowledging cognitive or stress-relieving benefits, the adverse outcomes overwhelmingly outweigh the positives. The paper also discusses the Indian government's 2025 regulatory intervention to mitigate online gaming's societal and economic repercussions.

Keywords: Online gaming, behavioural addiction, digital regulation and financial irregularity

Addiction is a phenomenon that adversely impacts the physiological as well as psychological well-being of the individual. There are various facets of addiction like substance addiction and non-substance addiction. On the one hand, substance addiction, implies substances as drugs that have addiction implicit like alcohol, cannabis, hallucinogens, opioids etc. On the other hand, non-substance addiction means behavioural addiction that tends to stimulate the brain's reward system like eating, video gaming, shop lifting and so on (Grant et al., 2010). In 2018, WHO classified gaming addiction as a modern disease as it hinders the person's personal as well as professional responsibilities.

In the 11th Revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) gaming disorder is defined as “a pattern of gaming behaviour characterized by impaired control over gaming, increasing priority given to gaming over other activities to the extent that gaming takes precedence over other interests and daily activities, and continuation or escalation of gaming despite the occurrence of negative consequences” (Chan et al., 2024). Across the world, this menace has destroyed the life of several individuals leaving them as well as their families broke.

Recently, India has declared online gaming addiction as a nationwide crisis after witnessing the vicious circle of borrowing

money, escalating debts, shame and ultimately suicide. A glimmer of hope came in the form of landmark judgement passed by Indian Parliament. With the passage of Promotion and Regulation of Online Gaming Bill, 2025, to promote and regulate other types of online games while protecting citizens from the threat posed by online money games (PIB, 2025). The purpose of this law is to prevent addiction, financial loss, and social suffering brought on by predatory gaming platforms that make false claims of rapid fortune.

Review of Literature

Psychological Impact and Gaming Disorder

Gao et al. (2024) found that online gaming addiction and loneliness were positively correlated. college students exhibiting high levels of sensation seeking experienced a strong impact from FoMO on OGA. According to Larrieu et al. (2022), escapers had worse psychological health, higher neuroticism, and functional impairment, despite the fact that both competitive and escaper players had higher IGD scores. Young adults experience stress and loneliness used it as a coping strategy, giving them a feeling of a sense of belonging. However, excessive gaming harmed family ties and social interactions (Park et al., 2024). 66% of gamers reported having bad sleep, and around half of the players had borderline psychological well-being (Matias et al., 2023).

Kishore and Rose (2023) asserted a negative association between irritation and social closeness, meaning that as irritability rises, social connectedness falls. A strong positive relationship between alexithymia and game addiction, as well as a significant negative connection between empathy and game addiction (Goel, 2023). Xavier's et al. (2023) found that online gaming addiction negatively impacts personal relationships, health, and emotional regulation. The academic achievement of online gamers, who were primarily men, was merely mediocre, but that of non-players was superior

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(Garcia et al., 2018). According to Wei et al. (2012), higher levels of sadness, social anxiety, and signs of internet addiction were associated with excessive weekly hours spent playing video games online. Excessive gaming frequently results in detrimental academic, emotional, and social effects and is associated with psychological, social, and personal issues (Limone et al., 2023). According to Zamani et al. (2009), computer game addiction is inversely correlated with social dysfunction and directly linked to students' physical issues, anxiety, sleep issues, and despair.

Avulasetty and Rotti (2023) Popular games included Candy Crush, PUBG, and Ludo. Excessive gaming like candy crush, PUBG, and Ludo has been connected to detrimental effects on social and psychological well-being, stress relief use, and physical problems such migraines and eye strain. Higher levels of tension, worry, and sadness were reported by students who were more addicted to gaming (Perez et al., 2024). According to Widiatoro et al. (2024), social isolation and video game addiction were found to be at moderate levels among Indonesian undergraduates. Online game addiction among Chinese college students negatively affected behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement leading to reduced academic achievement motivation. Learning engagement played a mediating role, meaning higher engagement could buffer the negative academic effects of gaming addiction (Sun et al., 2023).

Smartphone, social media, and internet game addiction among adolescents were found to significantly harm interpersonal interactions (Luo et al., 2023).

The bulk of male medical students played video games. Although some students said that modest gaming enhanced their focus or grades, prolonged gaming had a negative impact on sleep patterns, eating habits, physical fitness, and occasionally academic performance (Albaker et al., 2021). Indian children who are addicted to online gaming have serious challenges in their academic, social, emotional, and physical lives, such as poor performance, anxiety, depression, and trouble sleeping (Dhaka & Sharma, 2023). Internet addiction mediated a sizable amount of the relationship between social anxiety and loneliness, whereas increased weekly gaming time negatively moderated the relationship between internet addiction and loneliness (Osorio & Morales, 2025). 40.3% of teenagers are addicted to online games like PUBG. Problems with emotions, behavior, hyperactivity, and peers were all substantially linked to addiction, and vulnerability was raised by a lack of self-control (Singh et al., 2020). Online game addiction and poor mental health were found to be positively related in a study conducted among high school students in the Philippines during the Covid-19 outbreak (Perez et al., 2024). Vocational students who played online games too much experienced weariness, sleep issues, poor eating habits, back discomfort, eye strain, and decreased physical activity (Zaferina et al., 2024).

The Positive and Negative Impact of Online Gaming

Gaming has been connected to headaches, eyesight issues, sleep difficulties, decreased social contact, and compulsive behaviours, despite the fact that it also provided enjoyment, stress release, and cognitive advantages including better reflexes (Rani & Yadav, 2024). Playing MMORPGs affected the psychological well-being of teenagers and young adults in both ways. Although gaming promoted social connection, friendships, and enjoyment, it has also been connected to addiction, insomnia, depression, social disengagement, and scholastic challenges; in general, the negative

consequences of gaming outweigh the positive ones (Scott & Porter-Armstrong, 2013).

Video gaming improved mental health in Japan. Ownership of a console (Switch or PS5) increased life happiness and decreased psychological discomfort, with Switch users benefiting the most. Nevertheless, these advantages were diminished by playing for more than three hours every day, and the impacts differed depending on age, gender, and gaming platform (Vuorre et al., 2022). The excessive and unregulated gaming has been linked to depression, anxiety, poor sleep, scholastic decline, behavioral changes, and Internet Gaming Disorder, despite the fact that it can enhance hand-eye coordination, stress alleviation, and social relationships (Sharma & Awungshi, 2024). Teen addiction to mobile gaming was closely associated with academic decline, melancholy, social isolation, and insomnia. Although many people said that gaming helped them relax, reduce stress, and improve their skills. Excessive gaming frequently interfered with family obligations and relationships (Archana & Kumar, 2023). Teenagers having unfulfilled basic psychological needs like autonomy, competence, and relatedness were more susceptible to developing an addiction to online gaming. Nonetheless, accountability and purpose in life served as protective mediators, enhancing self-control and purpose and lowering the likelihood of addiction (Kaya et al., 2023).

Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to explore the detrimental impact of online gaming on the physical and the psychological well-being. There is a dearth of researches that pointed out the menace created by the online gaming. However, this paper highlighted the long-term impact that will be created as the youngster who indulged in the gaming as an adrenal rush will eventually lead into the vicious trap of gaming. The government of India had taken stringent steps against the online money-based gaming pattern that ruined the lives of several adults.

The first and the foremost aspect is that online gaming had taken a lot of tolls on the psychological well-being of the youngsters as well as adults. This issue emerges from a swing to a passive lifestyle, disregarding real-life activities leading to the challenging behaviour like emotional imbalance and encountering maladjustment in daily life events. According to the report of the Diplomat in 2024, "India's online gambling market is estimated to have 12.17 million users and is expected to grow by 8.5% a year". The major area of concern is the manifold stressors associated with it resulting in the mood symptoms and suicidal ideations. The unchecked upsurge of online gambling imperils youth mental health and dents the nation's economic growth, challenging immediate action and control.

The second aspect is the dual role of gaming on the mental health of the youngsters. There are certain studies that highlighted the positive impact of gaming. It points out that it will chisel the cognitive abilities of the youngsters and also increased the realms of connectedness, however the risks outweigh more than the benefits. The dependency on gaming gives the addicts a solace for short duration from the harsh realities of life. However, it serves as more detrimental for their mental health in long run.

Remedies

Recent research on online gaming and Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) has identified several effective remedies and intervention strategies to reduce excessive or problematic gaming behavior. In

addition to individual therapy, family-based and social support interventions play a crucial role in managing gaming addiction, especially among young people. Research highlights that parental involvement-through open communication, setting gaming boundaries, and encouraging offline family activities-can significantly reduce gaming dependency. Similarly, group counselling sessions in schools, which focus on self-control and peer support, have proven effective in helping students develop healthier digital habits. structured intervention programs delivered in educational or community settings. Such programs often include awareness sessions, time-management training, and counselling focused on self-regulation and emotional coping.

Furthermore, technology-assisted remedies, such as mobile applications and online self-monitoring tools that help individuals track their gaming time and receive reminders or suggestions for alternative activities. Overall, the literature recommends a multimodal approach that integrates CBT, family involvement, behavioral modification, and technological support. This comprehensive framework begins with screening and psychoeducation, followed by therapeutic interventions, lifestyle adjustments, and relapse prevention strategies.

Implications of the Study

The findings emphasize the urgent need for psychological awareness, preventive measures, and policy regulation to safeguard youth from the escalating menace of gaming addiction. There is an urgent need that the government safeguard families while guiding the digital economy towards safe and constructive growth.

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